

Relationship Between Socio-Economic Disadvantage and Depression Among Middle and High School Students in Kansas

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Abstract:

The Kansas Communities That Care (KCTC) Student Survey results has reported that the rate of students with depression slowly rose in Kansas from 2016 until 2022. Fortunately, the trend has reversed since 2022. Depression leads to a decline in concentration on classwork, less enthusiasm for studying, and lower achievement of grades. In this study, the author investigated the association between depression rate data from the KCTC Student Survey with health behaviors, socio-economic status, and poor mental health days data from the University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute's (UWPHI) county level data for adults. The participants of the two surveys belong to two different demographic groups except for the fact that they live in the same county. Results of the study indicate that the independent variables from the UWPHI's county level data are positively correlated with the depression rate from the KCTC Student Survey most often for grades 6, 8, 10, and 12, meaning increased level of social disadvantage in the community is associated with a higher rate of depression among students. Grade 10 students had the highest rate of depression consistently while grade 6 students had the lowest.

Key Words: Depression, Socio-Economic Disadvantage

1. Introduction

Research has reported that low socio-economic status has an association with higher prevalence of depression (Freeman et al., 2016, Modabber-Nia, 2007). According to Torikka et al. (2014) "the prevalence of depression increases significantly during the transition from childhood to adolescence with the highest incidence at ages 15 to 16." Najman, J. M. et al. (2010) reports that family poverty is a good predictor of adolescent and young adult anxiety and depression. Tracy, M. et al. (2008) reported that their findings are consistent with other studies that low family income is associated with higher levels of depressive symptoms in children and adolescents. Joinson, C. et al. (2017) reports that "Low SEP was associated with increased incidence rates of depressive symptoms in all age periods, with indicators of low standard of living showing the strongest associations." Gilman S. E. et al. (2003) concluded that "Childhood social disadvantage significantly influences risk of depression onset both in childhood and in adulthood."

The general objective of this study is to find out whether the socio-economic status of Kansans at county level has a correlation with the percentage of students with depression. This study has compared depression rate data from a state of Kansas school survey with socio-economic data from a different national survey at county level. Unfortunately, the school survey does not contain the socio-economic data of the students. The Kansas Communities That Care (KCTC) Student Survey has been conducted since 1994-95. The University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute (UWPHI) collects county level data which includes mental health variables and socio-economic

variables for all the counties annually. In general, their County Health Rankings Model explores the measures that influence how long and how well people live.

Participants of the two surveys are extremely unlikely to be the same individuals other than the fact that they live in the same county. The KCTC survey is completely anonymous, voluntary, and confidential. Since 2016, questions about depression and suicide thoughts, and suicide attempts have been included in the KCTC Student Survey. The KCTC Student Survey collects data from students in grades 6, 8, 10, and 12 annually. The average depression rate among Kansas students (6-12 grade) has increased from about 25% to 38% from 2016 to 2022 and gone down to 33% in 2024. Student Data Privacy Act of 2014 and changes to the act in 2022 has reduced the participation by about two-thirds since 2014 through 2023, though there was an increase between 2015 and 2020.

The first research question addressed in this study is whether there are associations between the KCTC Student Survey depression variables and the county level Health Behavior, Socio-Economic Factor, and Poor Mental Health Days variables from UWPHI. The second research question is to figure out which county level variable from UWPHI is most often associated with the KCTC rate of depression data. The third research question is to find out whether there is a difference between the rate of depression among grades.

Only 46 out of the 105 counties in Kansas have participated (or have large enough sample sizes) in the KCTC Student Survey at least 5 times between 2017 and 2024. According to KCTC Student Survey 2023-24 Depression/Supplementary Report, “In 2024, 90% of districts participating in KCTC survey also administered the optional depression/suicide module resulting in information from 28,032 students (15,996 middle school and 12,036 high school) from 155 districts and 7 private schools.” Using data from these 46 counties correlations were calculated between the rate of depression in grades 6, 8, 10, and 12 for each year against the national Z-scores for the three variables from the county level data for the respective year. Lower Z-scores from UWPHI data represent better living conditions. The KCTC Student Survey asked the question “During the past 12 months, did you ever feel so sad or hopeless almost every day for two weeks or more in a row that you stopped doing some usual activities?” to gather information about depression. The KCTC Student Survey pools data from all the grades to calculate the Total Depression Rate for each county.

Figure 1: Survey Participation

Reprinted from Kansas Communities That Care Student Survey Overview and Frequently Asked Questions, Retrieved October 24, 2024, from <https://kctcdata.org/school-administrators/survey-faqs/#Purpose>.

Figure 2: Total Rate of Depression 2016-2024

T-2016 represents the combined (total) percentage for all 4 grades in 2016

Figure 3: KCTC Student Participation Map

Reprinted from 2024 KCTC County Participation Optional Suicide/ Depression Module, Retrieved October 24, 2024, from <https://kctcdata.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Depression-Suicide-Participation-Map-2024.pdf>.

Figure 4: University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute’s County Health Ranking & Roadmap for Kansas in 2024

Reprinted from Kansas Health Institute, 2024 County Health Rankings: County Profiles, Retrieved October 24, 2024, from <https://www.khi.org/articles/2024-county-health-rankings-county-profiles/>.

Figure 5: County Health Rankings Model from University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute

Reprinted from University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute. County Health Rankings & Roadmaps 2024, Retrieved October 24, 2024, from <https://www.countyhealthrankings.org/health-data/methodology-and-sources/methods>.

The State of Kansas, Student Data Privacy Act of 2015 and the 2022 legislative changes to parent consent requirements had made drastic reductions in survey participation in 2015 and in 2022. Survey participation has increased from 2015 until 2020 but started to go down from 2020 until 2023 (Figure 1). Total depression rate gradually increased from 2016 until 2022 and started to go down (Figure 2). Participation of the optional Suicide / Depression Module of the survey is minimal in the population centers of the state (Figure 3). Johnson County and Wyandotte County at the extreme ends of the Healthy Factors Scale according to County Health Rankings and Roadmap have lowest participation in the KCTC Suicide / Depression Module of the survey (Figures 3 & 4). The County Health Rankings Model from University of Wisconsin Population Health Institute (Figure 5) explains how different policies, programs, and factors affect health outcomes. Policies and programs affect health factors which in turn affect the health outcomes they indicate as quality of life and length of life. The UWPHI measures the health factors as health behaviors (30%), clinical care (20%), social and economic factors (40%), and physical environment (10%). They collect the county level data in various ways and publish a national Z-score for each county for different health factors. In this study, Health Behaviors Z-Score, Social and Economic Factor Z-score, and Poor Mental Health Days Z-score have been used for the counties included in the study. From the KCTC Student Survey, Total Depression Rate for each grade in each county was included in the study.

2. Methodology

Correlations between interested variables were calculated and tests were conducted for testing Hypotheses 1-3. The Total Rate of Depression in the data came from different counties and they were neither close to 0 and nor close to 1. It is reasonable to use the correlation coefficient to study the strength and direction of the relationship. Z-tests were used to compare grade to grade percentages in Hypothesis 4.

H_{01} : Depression rate at each grade is not correlated to the health behaviors (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{A1} : Depression rate at each grade is positively correlated to the health behaviors (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{02} : Depression rate at each grade is not correlated to the socio-economic factors (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{A2} : Depression rate at each grade is positively correlated to the socio-economic factors (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{03} : Depression rate at each grade is not correlated to the poor mental health days (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{A3} : Depression rate at each grade is positively correlated to the poor mental health days (disadvantage) at the county level

H_{04} : Depression rates between grades are not different.

H_{A4} : Depression rates between grades are different.

3. Results

Figure 6 represents one example of the relationship between Total Depression Rate and Social & Economic Factor Z-Score. Since lower z-score values indicate better Social & Economic Outcomes and Social & Economic Factor Z-Score is used as a proxy for the socio-economic disadvantage, Figure 6 illustrates a positive relationship between socio-economic disadvantage and Total Depression Rate.

Figure 7 represents state averages of depression rate from 2016 to 2024. For each year, the depression rates have an ascending pattern in the order of Grades 6, 8, 12, and 10 except in 2024. Table 2 reports the number of significant individual Z-test results for each county in the selected 46 counties, if data were available, comparing classes 6 & 8, 6 & 10, and 12 & 10. As expected, the highest number of significant differences were between grades 6 and 10, but the highest among them were in 2017 with 13 significant tests among 46 tests. Only about 8% tests among 324 individual tests between grades 6 and 8 were significant, 3% tests among 315 individual tests between grades 10 and 12 were significant, and 21% tests among 315 individual tests between grades 6 and 10 were significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Figure. 6: Total Depression Rate in Grade 6 (2019) vs. Social & Economic Factor Z-Score

Lower z-score value indicates better Social & Economic Outcomes, higher value indicates worse Social & Economic Outcomes

Figure. 7: Depression Rate State Averages for Different Grades

Figure 8: Total Depression Rate for 2017, 2019 and 2022

Figure 8 shows that the Total Depression Rate has a symmetric pattern in 2017 with the highest rate of about 35%, skewed to the left distribution with highest rate close to 40% in 2019, and a symmetric distribution with highest rate close to 47% in 2022. Also, the scatterplots show that in general counties with lower rates continue to have lower rates while those with higher rates continue to have higher rates.

Table 1 reports the results of significant correlation tests between Total Depression Rate from the KCTC survey and the social disadvantage variables from UWPHI data. Most of the tests conducted using Social & Economic Factors Z-Score were statistically significant at 10% level of significance (21 out of 24) while 18 out of 24 tests were significant at the 5% level. Total Depression Rate in each grade and the Health Behaviors National Z-Scores were statistically significant at the 10% level of significance in 16 out of 24 tests conducted while 11 out of 24 tests were significant at the 5% level. Total Depression Rate in each grade considered and the Poor Mental Health Days National Z-Scores were significant at the 10% significance in 13 out of 24 while significant at the 5% for 10 among 24 tests conducted.

4. Conclusions

The Student Data Privacy Act of 2015 and its amendments to an opt in system in 2022 has reduced student participation significantly. Health Behaviors National Z-Score and Poor Mental Health Days National Z-Scores were not as often as significantly correlated with the Total Depression Rates, but the Total Depression Rates were highly correlated with the Socio-Economic Factors National Z-Score. Five out of eight years, the Total Depression Rate between grade 6 and grade 8 was significantly different as well as between grades 8 and 12 at 0.05 level of significance. Three out of eight years, the Total Depression Rate between grade 10 and grade 12 was significantly

different. Grade 6 consistently had the lowest Total Depression Rate while grade 10 had the highest. County-wise comparisons showed that the differences in Total Depression Rate for grade 6 vs. grade 8 and grade 10 vs. grade 12 were rare while a relatively higher proportion of counties had significant differences between grade 6 and grade 10.

In this paper, the analysis and results/conclusions expressed are those of the author.

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Significant Correlation Coefficients Between Rate of Depression in Grades and Health & Socio-Economic Variables Over the Years 2017-2024 (Testing H_1 , H_2 , and H_3)

Class-Year	Health Behaviors National Z-Score for the County r (p - Value)	Social & Economic Factors National Z- Score for the County r (p - Value)	Poor Mental Health Days National Z- Score for the County r (p - Value)
6G-2017	0.374 (0.014)	0.330 (0.027)	
8G-2017			
10G-2017	0.405 (0.009)	0.317 (0.036)	
12G-2017	0.529 (0.001)	0.429 (0.006)	0.511 (0.001)
6G-2018	0.228 (0.071)	0.438 (0.002)	
8G-2018			
10G-2018	0.360 (0.009)	0.277 (0.036)	0.272 (0.039)
12G-2018	0.204 (0.091)	0.225 (0.071)	
6G-2019	0.336 (0.012)	0.254 (0.046)	
8G-2019	0.369 (0.006)	0.382 (0.005)	0.308 (0.020)
10G-2019			
12G-2019	0.551 (0.001)	0.546 (0.001)	0.375 (0.006)
6G-2020	0.479 (0.001)	0.483 (0.001)	0.502 (0.001)
8G-2020		0.429 (0.002)	0.291 (0.030)
10G-2020		0.236 (0.057)	
12G-2020	0.275 (0.034)	0.338 (0.012)	0.280 (0.032)
6G-2021	0.398 (0.004)	0.273 (0.035)	0.388 (0.005)
8G-2021	0.223 (0.069)	0.336 (0.011)	0.208 (0.083)
10G-2021		0.251 (0.046)	0.208 (0.083)
12G-2021		0.238 (0.058)	0.280 (0.032)
6G-2022	0.326 (0.015)	0.512 (0.001)	0.279 (0.032)
8G-2022	0.205 (0.089)	0.320 (0.016)	
10G-2022	0.213 (0.081)	0.355 (0.009)	0.207 (0.086)
8G-2023		0.474 (0.003)	

Table 1: Correlation Test Results Between Total Rate of Depression and Socio-Economic Disadvantage Variables

County-wise Comparisons: Number of Counties with Significant Differences of Proportions								
Grades	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
6 vs. 8	1/36	3/43	7/44	6/46	3/46	3/45	5/31	4/33
10 vs. 12	2/32	3/43	0/44	1/46	1/46	1/45	2/28	0/30
6 vs. 10	6/32	6/41	11/44	10/45	13/46	9/45	9/31	3/31

Level of significance for each test was 0.05.

Table 2: Testing H_4 , County-wise Comparisons Between Selected Grades